

This document was produced by the committee of the Statistics and Law Section of the Royal Statistical Society¹ to summarise the available guides to statistics for legal and forensic practitioners.

Statistics and probability for advocates: Understanding the use of statistical evidence in courts and tribunals

Guide designed to enable advocates to more effectively understand, recognise and manage statistics and probability statements used by expert witnesses.

Endorsed by: The Inns of Court College of Advocacy, The Royal Statistical Society

Link: <http://www.rss.org.uk/Images/PDF/influencing-change/2017/ICCA-RSS-guide-version-6-branded-171019-REV03+designed-covers.pdf>

Four practitioner guides on the fundamentals of statistics and the law:

The guides look at communicating and interpreting statistical evidence in the administration of criminal justice. They are intended to assist judges, lawyers, forensic scientists and other expert witnesses in coping with the demands of modern criminal litigation.

- 1) [Fundamentals of probability and statistical evidence in criminal proceedings](#)
- 2) [Assessing the probative value of DNA evidence](#)
- 3) [‘The logic of forensic proof: inferential reasoning in criminal evidence and forensic science’](#)
- 4) [‘Case assessment and interpretation of expert evidence’](#)

Written by: Colin Aitken, Paul Roberts, Graham Jackson, Roberto Puch-Solis, Sue Pope

Endorsed by: Royal Statistical Society

Supported by: Nuffield Foundation

Judicial primers designed to assist the judiciary when handling scientific evidence in the courtroom (two published so far):

Collaboration between members of the judiciary, the Royal Society and the Royal Society of Edinburgh. Written by leading scientists and members of the judiciary, peer reviewed by practitioners.

Forensic DNA analysis: <https://royalsociety.org/~media/about-us/programmes/science-and-law/royal-society-forensic-dna-analysis-primer-for-courts.pdf>

Forensic gait analysis: <https://royalsociety.org/~media/about-us/programmes/science-and-law/royal-society-forensic-gait-analysis-primer-for-courts.pdf>

Endorsed by: The Royal Society and The Royal Society of Edinburgh

Making sense of forensic genetics

Guide designed to introduce professional and public audiences to the use of DNA in criminal investigations; to understand what DNA can and can't tell us about a crime, and what the current and future uses of DNA analysis in the criminal justice system might be

¹ Professor Jane Hutton (chair), Dr Amy Wilson (secretary), Professor Niamh Nic Daeid (vice chair), Professor Julia Mortera (meetings secretary), Professor Philip Dawid, Professor Joseph Gastwirth, Dr Alex Biedermann, Leigh-Ann Mulcahy QC, Professor Graham Jackson, Dr Claire Mclvor, Professor Peter Green, Professor Richard Goldberg, Dr Andy Sutherland

Endorsed by: Sense about science, European Forensic Genetics Network of Excellence

Link: <https://senseaboutscience.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/01/making-sense-of-forensic-genetics.pdf>

ENFSI guideline for evaluative reporting in forensic science

This guide provides a recommended framework for forensic practitioners to formulate evaluative casework reports

Written by: ENFSI experts led by Mrs Sheila Willis from Forensic Science Ireland

Endorsed and funded by: ENFSI

Link: <http://enfsi.eu/news/enfsi-guideline-evaluative-reporting-forensic-science/>

American Statistical Association (ASA) guidance on statistical statements for forensic evidence

In response to concerns that the use of forensic evidence such as shoe prints, fingerprints, bite marks, fibres, or hairs has contributed to wrongful convictions, the ASA produced a document with guidelines for discussing forensic evidence.

Endorsed by: ASA Forensic Science Advisory Committee

Adapted from a document developed by a subcommittee of the National Commission for Forensic Science.

Link: <https://www.amstat.org/asa/files/pdfs/POL-ForensicScience.pdf>

Link with more details: <https://www.amstat.org/asa/News/ASA-Issues-Guidance-on-Statistical-Statements-for-Forensic-Evidence.aspx>

UK forensic science regulator

The forensic science regulator produces a number of documents and guidelines for the reporting of forensic evidence. These can be found here:

<https://www.gov.uk/search/guidance-and-regulation?organisations%5B%5D=forensic-science-regulator&parent=forensic-science-regulator>